

**MEASURING EFFECTS OF LEARNING RESOURCES AND PROCESS
EVALUATION
RESEARCH PARTICIPANT INFORMED CONSENT FORM-ADULT**

Research project: Development and testing of digital learning resources for informed health choices and participation in informed dialogues about health in Rwanda (CHOICE PROJECT)

1. INTRODUCTION

CHOICE project is a research collaboration that seeks to improve health literacy by developing and testing of resources that can be used to enable young people to make informed personal choices about their health (health choices learning-resources) and to participate as scientifically literate citizens in informed debate about health policies (health policy learning-resources).

In Rwanda, the study is being conducted by researchers from University of Rwanda College of Medicine and Health Sciences and will involve continuous interaction with students, teachers, development partners, policy makers and researchers.

The information in this document is meant to help you decide whether or not to take part in this study but first they're a few things to note.

- You are being asked to participate in this research because you are a potential participant and an adult of legal consenting age.
- We anticipate that once you agree to participate you will be in the study for a period of 1-12 months.
- You will be offered a copy of this form for your future reference.
- Please feel free to ask if you have any questions or concerns at any time before the start or during the conduct of the research.

2. WHY IS THIS RESEARCH BEING CONDUCTED?

The aim of this collaborative research project is to improve population health outcomes by improving health literacy in low-income countries. We will do this by developing and evaluating two strategies for improving health literacy: resources that can be used to enable young people to make informed personal choices about their health (health choices learning-resources) and to participate as scientifically literate citizens in informed debate about health policies (health policy learning-resources).

3. HOW WILL THE STUDY BE CONDUCTED AND YOUR INVOLVEMENT?

The study will be conducted in over one 80 schools in Rwanda, during school term. Some schools will be allocated to the intervention arm and others to the control arm. All the selected schools will be allocated to either the intervention arm or to the control arm using computer-generated randomization.

Schools in the intervention arm together with their teachers will learn resources developed. In the control arm, students will continue with the curriculum as normal during the school term.

The claim evaluation tool will be given to each student to assess whether he/she was able to apply knowledge gained from the learning resources. All the students in both arms of the trial will complete the questionnaires in their classrooms at the end of the term. This questionnaire will require approximately one hour. We will administer the questionnaires again after one year to find out if the children retained what they learned. All the schools that were allocated to the control arm will also get the learning resources after the trial has been concluded and the CLAIM questionnaires have been collected. In addition to the data from the CLAIM evaluation tools, we will ask your school to provide us with data on student's class performance on the ministry of education curriculum (end of terms scores) as well as their attendance data for the period of the trial. We will interview some teachers, education officers and students from schools in the intervention arm regarding the process of using resources.

4. POSSIBLE RISKS TO YOU

We anticipate that your participation in the study/research presents no risk to you as an individual. However, participation in this study might in some way interfere with your work if you are required to participate in study activities during work hours.

5. POSSIBLE BENEFITS TO YOU

There will be no direct benefit to you from participating in this study and there is no promise of gaining any material or financial benefit from the project currently or in the future. Your participation in the study will equip you with skills to enable you obtain, process and understand health information that you need to make appropriate healthcare decisions. You will benefit from free health information.

6. COST TO THE PARTICIPANT

You will incur no cost whatsoever other than time as a result of taking part in the study.

7. COMPENSATION

You will not gain any form of compensation, monetary or otherwise for participating in the study but appropriate daily expenses in form of lunch and transport will be reimbursed if you attend any study-related meetings or workshops.

8. CONFIDENTIALITY

The information you give during the conduct of this research will be kept confidential in accordance to the ethical standards agreed upon by the local and international organizations governing the conduct of research involving human participants. Any information resulting from this study, if published in scientific journals or presented at scientific meetings, will not reveal your identity.

9. CONSENT TO THE USE OF VIDEO AND PHOTOS FOR THE INFORMED HEALTH CHOICES PROJECT

We would like to use video and photos to help people learn about the project and learning resources. They will be used in learning resources, on the project website; in presentations at meetings and conferences; in scientific journals; in the news media; and in social media, such as Twitter and Facebook. If you sign this form, you give us permission to use the video and/or photos of you, or the child for whom you are responsible and you can revoke (take back) your permission to use the video and/or photos, but this will only apply to future use, meaning the videos and/or photos will not be removed where they have already been used. This form will be kept securely by the project, but it may be shared with others who wish to use the videos or photos, for example scientific journals.

10. RIGHT TO REFUSE/WITHDRAW

Your participation in this research is purely voluntary and you are free to decline to take part or withdraw at any time without any repercussions.

11. QUESTIONS ABOUT THE RESEARCH

In case of any further questions, please contact Prof. Laetitia NYIRAZINYOYE, the Principal Investigator in Rwanda working at University of Rwanda College of Medicine and Health Sciences, Kigali Rwanda: Tel: 0788683209 or Mr. Michael MUGISHA on 0788596947.

In case of questions in regards to research ethics, you may contact **Dr Jean Baptiste MAZARATI** on tel: **0788 309 807**, Chairperson, Rwanda National Ethics Committee or Dr. Tumusiime David Secretary of RNEC on tel: **0788749398**.

12. DECLARATION OF CONSENT

The information about this study has been availed and explained to me and all my questions have been answered. I have read this form and I feel that I have had enough information and time to consider my decision to join the study. I fully understand that by signing this form, I do not waive any of my legal rights, nor does it relieve the study investigators their duty (liability), but merely indicates that I have been informed about the research study in which I am voluntarily agreeing to take part. A copy of this form will be availed to me. Having understood all the information pertaining to this study I therefore agree to my participation in this study by appending my signature and name below.

Research Participant

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Tel number:

Study Participant consent to use your video and/or photo in the project

Your signature: _____ Date _____